

AN ANALYSIS OF SUBTITLING STRATEGIES: A CASE OF ENGLISH AND INDONESIAN LANGUAGE PAIR

Zulva Ratusmanga,

Novriyanto Napuⁱ

Universitas Negeri Gorontalo,
Indonesia

Abstract:

The aimed of this study is to find out the subtitle strategies found in the Ride Along Movie through English subtitles into Indonesian subtitle. This research used a descriptive qualitative method. The results of this research show that not all parts of subtitling strategies are used. The findings revealed that there are only five strategies out of ten subtitling strategies proposed by Gottlieb (1992, p.166) used in Ride Along movie. The strategies include expansion (one data), paraphrase (six data), imitation (eight data), decimation (four data) and deletion (one data). It shows that imitation is mostly used followed by expansion, paraphrase, decimation, and deletion consequently.

Keywords: translation, subtitle, subtitling strategies

1. Introduction

Subtitling is a complex form of translation in which the spoken language (source language) of the film is translated into the written language of the viewing audience (target language). Subtitling is very important in the film because subtitles can help the audience understand the film. They are usually displayed at the bottom of the screen. According to Gambier (1993, p.276 cited in Hastuti, 2015, p.59) "*subtitling is one of two possible methods for providing the translation of a movie dialogue, where the original dialogue soundtrack is left in place, and the translation is printed along the bottom of the film. It means that through subtitling the audience of the foreign movie can enjoy the movie by reading the translating text on the bottom of the screen without ambiguous thinking.*"

However, subtitling is not an easy task to accomplish because one has to understand the rules in making subtitle. Therefore, to be a subtitler needs subtitling strategies. Gottlieb (1992, p.166) proposed that subtitling strategies consist of expansion, paraphrase, transfer, imitation, transcription, dislocation, condensation, decimation,

ⁱ Correspondence: email n.napu@ung.ac.id

deletion, and resignation. Through subtitling strategies, the subtitler will be easier to make a subtitle.

Based on the facts explained above, the researchers are interested in analyzing subtitling strategies in Ride Along Movie is used subtitling strategies proposed by Gottlieb (1992, p.166). This study attempts to classify the subtitling strategies through English subtitles into Indonesian subtitles in Ride Along Movie. The researchers have chosen the movie because this movie has a unique linguistics feature that indicated with the Subtitle. For example, in this film, the researchers found that there was so much pragmatic meaning from SL in this movie. According to Newmark (1988, p.47) *“communicative translation treats the following items similarly: stock and dead metaphors, pragmatic meaning, normal collocations, technical terms, slang, colloquialisms, standard notices, physicists, and ordinary language.”* Based on the example above, it can be seen that all related to the linguistics feature. This study is intended to examine the subtitling strategies applied in Ride Along Movie with a case English to Indonesian language pair.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Definition of Translation

Translation has always been a central part of communication. There are many definitions of translation. According to Nida & Taber (1982, p. 12) *“translating consists in reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the source language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style.”* Based on the explanation above, it can be inferred that translation is a process to change a sentence from the source language into the target language, but the language could be equivalent both in meaning and style. It is similarly proposed by Catford (1965, p.26) that translation is *“the replacement of textual material in one language (Source Language) by equivalent textual material in another language (Target Language).”*

In addition, Translation is not only a process to transfer a meaning or a message from one language into another, but also transferring ideas, seeking the equivalent to keeping the meaning from source language text into the target language text understandable. Youseff (2000, p.13) that translation is only to transfer the idea. It means that the reader of the translated text gets the information as they are reading the original text. Therefore, in translating a text from English to Indonesian, the translation must keep the information from the source language text to the target language text.

Newmark (1988, p.21) state that there are two approaches to translating: (1) you start translating sentence by sentence, for say the first paragraph or chapter, to get the feel and the feeling tone of the text, and then you deliberately sit back, review the position, and read the rest of the SL text; (2) you read the whole text two or three times, and find the intention, register, tone, mark the difficult words and passages and start translating only when you have taken your bearings.

Furthermore, to produce a good translation, the translator is not merely transferring SL to TL, but also the translator should pass some processes in translation.

This process means an activity that doing by translators in translation (Nababan, 1999, p.24). Thus, the process of translation consists of some steps in order to produce a good translation. They are analyzing, transferring, and similarly. Here are the following explanations:

- Analysis, the analysis becomes the first phase of the translation process because the analysis is used for knowing the message that will be translated and establish the relationship between the various elements of a sentence.
- Transferring, this step is trying to transfer the idea or message from SL to TL.
- Restructuring is trying to rearrange each sentence and making a new structure in the TL.

Based on the explanations above, it can be inferred that translating Source Language into Target Language has several processes or steps that need to be considered to produce a good translation, because translating is not just a process to transfer a meaning or a message from one language into another, but also transferring ideas, seeking the equivalent to keeping the meaning from source language text into the target language text.

2.2 Audio-Visual Translation

A movie is one of the television programs that many people in the world loved that. For example, Indonesian movie not only watched by Indonesian people but also other people from another country. In addition, a Hollywood movie is a movie that many people loved. However, many people in Indonesia still cannot understand the English language in the Hollywood movie. Therefore, the film producers must translate English as the source language to specific target language, in this case, the Indonesian language in order to make the audience easier to understand and enjoy the films. (Darma, 2014).

The translation used in movies is Audio-Visual Translation (AVT). Chiaro (2009: 141) described that audiovisual translation is transferring written text from one language to another of the verbal components contained in audiovisual works and products. It means that Audio-Visual Translation (AVT) is a process to transfer the equivalence meaning from Source Language to Target language that used in movies or audio devices. Moreover, Bordwell and Thompson (1990: 409) said that on Audio-Visual Translation (AVT) there are two major types that exist; dubbing and subtitling. Bordwell and Thompson (1990: 409) further stated that *"dubbing is the process of replacing part or all of the voices on the soundtrack in order to correct mistakes or rerecord dialog."* It means that dubbing is a process to replace the voice in "soundtrack" to correct the mistakes and re-record the voice. Subtitling is truly different from dubbing. Meanwhile, Gambier (1993: 276) explored his definition about subtitling as follow: *"Subtitling is one of two possible methods for providing the translation of a movie dialogue, where the original dialogue soundtrack is left in place, and the translation is printed along the bottom of the film"*. In other words, it can be said that subtitling is done by translating the film's dialogues

then put the printed translation in the bottom of the film. Similarly, as dubbing, the purpose of subtitling is helping the viewers to enjoy the films.

Hatim and Mason (2000, p.437) in *Politeness in Screen Translating* state that there are four kinds of difficulties working on subtitling. The first one is the shift in mode from speech to writing. It means that utterances conveyed in the film are translated in the form of writing by following the rules that exist in translating the film. The second is the factor which governs the medium or channel in which meaning is to be conveyed. Therefore, to translate a film, the subtitler must convey the meaning according to the existing context. The third one is the reduction of the source text as a consequence of the above. Therefore, subtitler must be able to ensure that a subtitle can be read and understood easily in a unit, just as we understand the complete text. The last is the requirement of matching the visual image. The subtitler must be able to match the phrase in each scene according to the context. The source text is translated into the target text by not changing the actual meaning.

Furthermore, Gottlieb (1992, p.164) discusses in different terminology, what he calls the formal (quantitative) and textual (qualitative) constraint of subtitling. The formal (quantitative) Constraints are the space factor (a maximum of two lines are allowed, with approximately 35 characters per line) and the time factor. The time factor, in particular, plays a pivotal role in the decisions translators have to make, although traditionally five to six seconds have been considered to be sufficient for reading a two-line sentence. Whereas, the textual (*qualitative*) constraints those imposed on the subtitles by the visual context of the film.

In addition, Cahyani (2012) stated that "*subtitling translators are also faced with difficult conditions of time appearance of subtitling.*" Hariyanto (2005, cited in Hastuti, 2015, p.59) said that there are some provisions the time of appearance of subtitling, namely: "*the duration to two full lines is 3-6 seconds, the duration of a single line (7-8 words) is less than 3.5 seconds, the duration of subtitling a single word is 1.5 seconds, a time figures emerged after the speech was 0.25 seconds, a figure of speech is gone after 2 seconds, the time between two successive subtitlings is 0.25 seconds*".

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the subtitle is used to translate the film from the source language to the target language that usually appears on the bottom of the screen, but to become a subtitler is not easy. To translate the film, Subtitling must be able to show a translation in accordance with existing rules.

2.3 Subtitling Strategies

Translating and subtitling have some different rules on the process of transferring text from one language to another. Different from the common translation that has no limit on the result in the target text, subtitling has a limit. That is why subtitling has its strategies. This research focuses on the Gottlieb (1992, p. 166) theory that is about Subtitling Strategies. According to Gottlieb (1992, p. 166) "*subtitle devised ten strategies which are used by subtitlers, including expansion, paraphrase, transfer, imitation, transcription, dislocation, condensation, decimation, deletion, and resignation.*"

- Expansion is used when the SL (Source Language) requires an additional explanation in translation because of some cultural nuance not retrievable in TL (Target Language).
- Paraphrase is used when the subtitler does not use the same syntactical rules in subtitling the dialogue. In other words, using this strategy, the subtitler changes the structures of the subtitle and makes it easier to understand and readable by the audience.
- Transfer there is no added explanation or modifying of view because the subtitler translates the dialogue by literal word. Also, the usage of this strategy maintains the structure of the original text.
- Imitation is re-writing the word the original text. Imitation is usually used to deal with the name of person, place, names of magazine, journals, newspapers, and the titles of as yet untranslated literary works, name of company and institutions, and addresses.
- Transcription is used in those cases where a term is unusual even in the source text; for example, the use of a third language, or nonsense language.
- Dislocation is adopted when the original employs a special effect; for example, a silly song in cartoon film, where the translation of the effect is more important than the content.
- Condensation is making the text brief to miss unnecessary utterance using the shorter utterance, but it does not lose the message. Sometimes the pragmatic effect can be lost by using condensation strategy. Therefore, the real aim of the text must be conveyed.
- Decimation is used to translate when the actors are quarreling with fast speaking. So, the translator is also condensing the utterance because the utterances have difficulty absorbing unstructured written text quickly.
- Deletion refers to the elimination of parts of a text.
- Resignation is used to describe the strategy adopted when no translation solution can be found, and meaning is inevitably lost.

3. Material and Methods

3.1 Method of Research

This research used a descriptive qualitative method because the purpose of this study is to describe the phenomenon of translation, particularly the subtitle strategies which is used in Ride Along Movie through English subtitles into Indonesian subtitles, then classify into ten subtitling strategies based Gottlieb theory (1922, p.166). In translation studies, a qualitative approach is used to understand a translation phenomenon based on its natural context (Napu, 2016). The data of this research are linguistics feature words to the utterance that indicate subtitling strategies, according to Gottlieb (1992, p.166). Source of data in this research is the utterance of the English Subtitle and Indonesian Subtitle in Ride Along Movie.

Data collected were classified and presented in the table. The table is to help in finding the subtitling strategies that applied in Ride Along Movie. On the table, there is English Subtitle as the Source Language and Indonesian subtitle as the Target Language. Source text is put on the left side, and the target text is put on the right side of the table. After the data were put in the table, the researchers compare between English Subtitle and Indonesian subtitle that aim to classify the data into ten subtitling strategies according to Gottlieb (1992, p.166) consists of expansion, paraphrase, transfer, imitation, transcription, dislocation, condensation, decimation, deletion, and resignation.

After the researchers classifying the data into ten subtitling strategies proposed by Gottlieb, the researchers identified every subtitling strategy in the Ride Along Movie. Explaining is aimed to describe the results obtained by the researchers. After all the data are classified into ten subtitling strategies, the researchers will be able to know and to describe the subtitling strategies applied in Ride Along Movie based on a theory proposed by Gottlieb (1992, p.166).

4. Results and Discussion

The research finding used data tabulation. Tabulation of data is the creation of a table containing various data that already contains the code in accordance with the analysis needed. Arikunto (1998) argues that data tabulation is a method of general description which includes scoring (giving scores) on various items that need to be scored and giving a code to any item items that do not have a score and then described in a table. In the data description, the researchers tabulated the finding data as below:

Table 1: Subtitling Strategies Used in Subtitle Text of Ride Along Movie

No	Subtitling Strategies	Data
1	Expansion	1
2	Paraphrase	6
3	Transfer	0
4	Imitation	8
5	Transcription	0
6	Dislocation	0
7	Condensation	0
8	Decimation	4
9	Deletion	1
10	Resignation	0
	Total	20

From the table above, it can be seen that the researchers found five (5) from ten (10) types of subtitling strategies by Gottlieb (1992, p.166) in Ride Alone movie. It shows that imitation is mostly used followed by expansion, paraphrase, decimation, and deletion consequently.

The discussion divided into the sub-items of the strategy of subtitling.

4.1 Expansion

Expansion is used when the Source Language (SL) requires an additional explanation in translation because of some cultural nuance not retrievable in Target Language (TL).

Example:

Source Language : *So is this about you becoming a cop?*

Target Language : *Jadi ini apa tentang keinginanmu untuk menjadi seorang polisi?*
(00.06.58->00.07.00)

Based on the data above, the meaning of the utterance in The Source Language "*So is this about you becoming a cop?*" should when translated into the target language became "*jadi apa ini tentang kamu menjadi seorang polisi?*" Therefore, used the expansion strategies because the subtitler adds words to the utterances in the target language that aims to provide additional explanations related to the context. Because in the context of the film, the utterance conveyed by Angela is a question, so when translated to target language the subtitler add a word "*apa*" to help the audience know that it is a question. In addition, the context in that film Ben and his girlfriend were discussing Ben's plan and desire to become a police officer, so when translated in Target Language, the subtitler added the word "*keinginanmu untuk*" to make the viewers and readers more understand about that utterance.

4.2 Paraphrase

Paraphrases in the translation are gaining how meaning created in the text as important information. In a simple explanation, the paraphrase is a paraphrase expresses a statement, a phrase or a single word, in some other words (Pernilla, 2007, p. 11).

Example:

Source Language : *Get out the way*

Target Language : *Minggir* (00.03.59)

Based on the data above, the utterance from Source Language "*Get Out the Way*" when translated into Target Language should Be "*keluar dari sana*". However, the subtitler translated became "*Minggir*". The subtitler changed the subtitle but is not changes the meaning of the utterance. In the context of the film, the situation looked very chaotic; at that moment, James was chasing one of Omar's work partners who had escaped with a car. Then James chased him with a car also. At that time the road seemed very crowded, there were many vehicles passing by. James then found it difficult to chase the person because many vehicles blocked him. Therefore, James said, "*Get out the way,*" which aims to ask other vehicles to get away from the road. Therefore, the subtitler changes the utterance from the source language to target language "*Get out the way*" became "*minggir*" because it was more suited to the context

in the film. That way, the audience easier reads the subtitle and understand about James meant.

4.3 Imitation

Imitation is re-writing the word the original text. Imitation is usually used to the words that refer with the name of person, place, names of magazine, journals, newspapers, titles of as yet untranslated literary works, name of company and institutions, and addresses.

Example:

Source Language: *get eyes on the sniper?!*

Target Language: *lihat sniper. (00.05.51)*

Based on the data above, the utterance of Source Language “get eyes on the sniper” when translated into Target Language became “lihat sniper”. Should when translated into the target language it becomes “lihat penembak jitu”. Pay attention to the word “sniper” when translated to Target Language does not become “penembak jitu” but still being a “sniper”. Therefore, this utterance uses the imitation strategy because the subtitler re-writes the word the original text “Sniper”. A word “Sniper” is a term or name given to a person as a sign of her/himself that have good skill in shooting a gun. Thus, the translator rewrites the word “Sniper” because it is an object name or terms in the move, and it called an imitation strategy in subtitling.

4.4 Decimation

Decimation is used to translate when the actors are quarreling with fast speaking. So, the translator is also condensing the utterance because the utterance has difficulty in absorbing unstructured written text quickly.

Example

Source Language : *Oke I don't know if you are being sarcastic, but I am not.*

Right now, I am on a black big op.

Target Language : *Oke, aku harap bisa ngobrol denganmu.*

Tapi sekarang aku sedang beroperasi. (00.05.36->05.39)

From the data above, some of the utterances was ignored by the translator. The reason was that the actors are speaking to fast in this scene. Thus, the subtitling is a type of decimation. It can be seen in the utterance “Oke I don't know if you are being sarcastic, but I am not, right now I am on a black big op.” should be “oke aku tidak tahu apakah kamu sedang menyindir, tapi aku tidak bisa. Aku sedang dalam operasi hitam yang besar”. However, the translator translated becomes “Oke, aku harap bisa ngobrol denganmu. Tapi sekarang aku sedang beroperasi”. Subtitler makes the Target Language was simpler, but is not

changed the meaning of the utterance from Source Language that aims to make the audience easier to read the subtitle.

4.5 Deletion

Deletion is referring to the elimination of parts of a text. Deletion in this research was used in this research in order to delete an utterance where the researchers consider not important, such as repetition, filler words, and question tags.

Example

Source Language : Freeze! I said freeze!

Target Language : Jangan bergerak! (00.02.49->00.04.15)

Based on the data above, the utterance from Source Language "*Freeze! I said freeze!*" when translated into Target Language should become "*jangan bergerak! Aku katakan jangan bergerak!*" but the subtitler just translated to Target Language became "*Jangan bergerak*". Therefore, subtitlers use the deletion strategy because word repetition occurs in the Source Language "*Freeze! I said freeze!*". In the context of the film, Ben and his friends as police officers are pursuing Omar's partner who wants to do illegal weapons business. At that time, the situation looked very chaotic because of the shooting in everywhere. Then Ben says, "*Freeze, I said Freeze,*" which aims to ask the target to stop so that Ben will not shoot him. The utterance from Source Language "*Freeze, I said Freeze*" translated into Target Language just became "*jangan bergerak*". From the utterance, it can be seen that the subtitler does not translate the meaning of the utterance "*I said freeze*" because in that situation Ben looks very hasty in pursuing the target, therefore the utterance "*Freeze, I said Freeze*" is only translated to be "*jangan bergerak*" which aims to make the audience easier to read the subtitles. The subtitler does not translate the other words because at the first utterance already represents translated the second utterance. In addition, the subtitler doesn't display it because the utterance won't last long in the scene.

5. Recommendations

From the analysis, this research addresses some suggestion that might be taken as consideration for some aspects.

- For translation teachers; in the teaching and learning process, especially in translation subject, subtitling can be integrated with the syllabus of the subject. So, the students can learn more about the material of the subtitle, how to make subtitles in movies and know about subtitling strategies in translation subject.
- For students; since the finding has described subtitling strategies in the movie. Thus, this study can be essential for the students especially for English Department Students to understand about subtitle in enriching their ability in making a movie subtitle.

- For the further studies; subtitling movie may be interesting for English students, so it can be suggested for the further researchers to conduct another research in order to find out another aspect of subtitling strategy in another movie. Thus, the researchers can compare and find out the results of subtitling strategies that are used in research and the results of research conducted by other researchers.

6. Conclusion

The researchers found that not all strategy of subtitling by Gottlieb (1992, p.166) that used by the subtitler in translating the source language to the target language because not all the utterances can be translated by using those strategies. The subtitling strategy which can be found in this subtitle was five strategies are transfer, transcription, dislocation, and resignation. All the strategies that the researchers found in this research are Expansion has one data, paraphrase has six data, imitation has eight data, decimation has four data, and deletion has one data. In other words, imitation is the most subtitle strategy that the translator used in Ride Along Movie.

About the Author(s)

Zulva Ratusmanga received her bachelor degree in English education from the Department of English Education, Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. Her research interest is in translation.

Novriyanto Napu is an active faculty member at the Department of English Education of Universitas Negeri Gorontalo. He holds a PhD in applied linguistics from the University of South Australia. His main research focuses on translation studies and English language teaching.

References

- Arikunto, Suharsimi. *Prosuder Penelitian Suatu Pendekatan Praktek*, Jakarta. 1998.
- Baker, M. *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies*, London and New York, 2001
- Bordwell & Thompson. *Film Art*. USA: McGraw- Hill, Inc, 1990, pp.409.
- Carstensen, K. *Developing a model of process strategies in subtitling: Redefining translation strategies taking a process perspective*. Department of Business, 2015.
- Cahyani, H. Penerjemahan Film dan Tantangannya: *Study Kasus Serial Film "Sex and The City"*. 2012. Retrieved from Polinema: <http://jlt-polinema.org/?p=67> . Accessed October 29, 2016.
- Catford, J. C. *A Linguistics Theory of Translation*. Oxford University Press. 1965, pp 26
- Chiaro, D. *Issues in Audiovisual Translation*. 2009, pp 141. Retrieved from routledge: <http://cw.routledge.com/textbooks/translationstudies/data/samples/9780415396417.pdf>. Accessed June 14, 2017.

- Darma, I. N. *An Analysis of Subtitling Strategies in The Magic of Belle Isle Movie*. 2014. Retrieved from: <https://ojs.unud.ac.id/index.php/sastra/article/view/8355>. Accessed October 22, 2016.
- Gambier, Yves. "Audio Visual Communication: Typological Detour". *Teaching Translation and Interpreting 2*. Philadelphia: John Benjamin. 1993, pp. 276
- Gambier & Gottlieb. *(Multi) Media Translation: concepts, practices, and research*. University of Copenhagen. 2001.
- Gottlieb, H. *Teaching Translation and Interpreting: Training, talent and experience*. University of Copenhagen. 1992, pp. 164-166
- Gottlieb, H. *Text, Translation and Subtitling in Theory, and in Denmark*. Universitas of Copenbagen. 2001
- Gottlieb & Mogensen. *Dictionary Visions, Research and Practice*. University of Copenhagen. 2004.
- Hastuti, E. D. *An Analysis on Subtitling Strategies Of Romeo And Juliet Movie*. 2015. Retrieved from [iainsalatiga: http://journalregister.iainsalatiga.ac.id/index.php/register/article/view/324](http://journalregister.iainsalatiga.ac.id/index.php/register/article/view/324). Accessed November 10, 2016.
- Hatim and Mason. *Politeness in Screen Translating*. London and New York. 2000, pp.437
- Hornby, M. S. (1995). *Translation Studies: An Integrated Approach*. USA: John Benjamins Publishing Company. 1995.
- Larson, M. L. *Meaning Based Translation, A Guide to Cross-language Equivalence*. University Press of America. 1984.
- Nababan, M. R. *Teori Menerjemahkan Bahasa Inggris*. 1999. Retrieved from: http://www.goodreads.com/book/show/2160823.Teori_Menerjemah_Bahasa_Inggris. Accessed January 12, 2017.
- Nababan, M. R. *Pengembangan model penilaian kualitas terjemahan*. 2012. Retrieved from: [publikasiilmiah: https://publikasiilmiah.ums.ac.id/bitstream/handle/11617/2220/4.%20MANGAT UR%20NABABAN.pdf?sequence=1](https://publikasiilmiah.ums.ac.id/bitstream/handle/11617/2220/4.%20MANGAT%20UR%20NABABAN.pdf?sequence=1). Accessed November 15, 2016.
- Napu, N. *Translation Tourism: Understanding the Quality of Translation Across Multiple Perspectives*. Doctoral Thesis. University of South Australia. Adelaide.
- Newmark, P. *A Textbook of Translation*. London: Prentice Hall. 1988, pp.21-47.
- Nida and Taber. *The Theory and Practice of Translation*. Leiden: E. J. Brill. 1982, pp.12
- Simanjuntak, N. V. *Subtitling Strategies in "Real Steel" Movie*. 2013. Retrieved from: http://eprints.dinus.ac.id/8208/1/jurnal_12373.pdf. Accessed October 23, 2016.
- Yousef, F. A. *Normative and Abstract Representation in Translation*. 2000, pp.13 Retrieved from: [Publications: http://Publications.edu.sa/](http://Publications.edu.sa/). Accessed January 05, 2017.

Zulva Ratusmanga, Novriyanto Napu
AN ANALYSIS OF SUBTITLING STRATEGIES:
A CASE OF ENGLISH AND INDONESIAN LANGUAGE PAIR

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Applied Linguistics Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).